

Geopathy, Earth and Human Connection: Natural Communication

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Abstract

Bio-Architect Mayank Barjatya works with geopathy and geobiology as a medium to learn from nature. He has been instrumental in analytical Earth assessment and its impact on human health and brain connections. He proposes the model and method by which detailed geobiological study can provide us information to derive the parameters for sustainable urban planning, construction & location of buildings, underground structures, and services that actually support and promote human health and well-being.

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1.1. Introduction to Geopathy

Humans have always been sensitive to certain places or areas where we do not sleep well, fall ill easily, or where our performance is lower. Dowsers and geo-biologists termed such zones as biological stress zones. The knowledge of this influence of the Earth (geos) on living beings (bios) is called Geobiology. Alternately the study of disease (pathos) caused by Earth (geos) is called Geopathy. This has also been called Geomancy in the past, with the suffix 'mancy' referring to the process of divination based on the Earth.

1.2. Natural Vibrations and the Human Body

The world sees the interaction of humans with their space with a specific eye. Vibration is the key element that affects each life-form. Under Earth elements includes grid lines, meridians, water streams, lakes, Earth cracks, shafts, earth cavities and also earth0sky chimneys. All the Earth elements are foreign to human energies and their wavelengths do not match with human wellbeing.

Multiple cultures and experts have proposed the model of the human being as an antenna, legs connected to the negative pole of the strata, and head connected to the positive pole of the cosmos. The human body is thus continuously a part of perennial energy exchange between the poles. This energy nourishes and sustains the human body.

Though we are not consciously aware of this process, our body does participate in it. It receives and stores this energy and information in its cells, whereon it goes on to influence the day to day workings of a human being. Resonance is the science of communication when two bodies or objects have similar wavelengths and frequencies irrespective of this location or distance. Morphogenetic field theory is based on this knowledge as stated by Rupert Sheldrake.

Following the same process of resonance, Earth and human communicates through the medium of the under Earth elements which is mainly 70% water, common in both.

1.3. The Tradition Behind Geobiology

Since long and referred to in books of history, the process to select the suitable land to make a home had documented parameters and rituals. In India, the Vedic wisdom holders had recorded the science of building construction named Vastu Shastra [2], the basis of this invention was scientific knowledge acquired through their

supersensory perceptions and practical self-application (“Tapobal”).[3] Science today has little knowledge of these facts and theories. The sages had a detailed knowledge of planetary cosmic forces and they were aware of its impact on the wellbeing of a human.

Figure 1 Lord Vishwakarma (God of creation & vastu)

Much before the invention of modern sciences, Indian forefathers had knowledge of these forces “ Vedas” has described these forces in the chapters. Even in ancient times, the sages were aware of the gravitational and magnetic effect of the Earth. Indian Vedic texts have detailed the effect of cosmic forces much before scientists in other parts of the world noticed.

Vastu Shastra principles have always considered the geobiological impact of Earth grid of energy lines revolving around the globe. The German physician Dr. Ernest Hartmann [4] later scientifically discovered these grid lines. Swiss Geobiologist, Blanche Merz, has discovered that by taking into account the measurements of Earth radiations, we can build or amplify the needed power point of the strongest vibration based on four themes – orientation, strong radioactivity, vertical strata and an absence of all trouble making Hartmann intersections inside the living space.

Understanding these principles, we can learn more about Brahma Sthala [6] which is much talked about in Vastu Shastra. Vastu Shastra is a building science which describes a balance between the human beings and their environment. We can achieve peace and prosperity by following the science of vastu during the construction. Home and working space constructed utilizing the parameters of Vedic Vastu Shastra which has a universal impact remains pleasant and prosperous. Feng Shui [7], is the Chinese interpretation of Vastu Shastra. It is the system of analyzing a landscape and its influence on a space. Energy (Chi) is the potential vibrations as per the shape of mountain, lakes, rivers, and forests, their size, disposition and the relationship between them also matters and is the deciding force to check the suitability of the site.

1.4. The Natural Invisible Order

Since ages and in history, the chosen site or plot of land would be verified before using it for multiple purposes. The decision for public buildings was based on the auspiciousness after special rituals, Gods’ dedications, the influence of planets, or order of the Saint. As per Architect Vitruvius, Roman’s were one of the first to determine the healthiness of a site by checking the entrails of the cows who were forced to live on the site for a year. Symbolism was considered most important. Time of construction of Escorial Palace in Spain was matched with the entrance of Sun and Moon in Aries to attain the highest military and political ambitions. The plan of this building was given the shape of a grill following the similarity to St. Laurence (martyr tortured on a grill). Pillar of the world “ Axis Mundi “ as per the ancients was critical factor which would help architects to determine the orientation and position in relation to the sun, Earth, and planets.

Figure 2 labyrinth stone circle

Figure 3 Stone Henges: Earth Puncture

A natural and invisible order was seen as an Image to understand architecture by the ancients. The subtle realms material form was seen in Mayan temples, Chinese pagodam Indian spiritual spaces and Gothic cathedrals. Few older carpenters in the Alps respect the forest and the wood and trees are felled only during a very specific period, between December and February, following descending moon. While building each beam, rafter and stud are specifically positioned according to the original direction of growth of the construction wood. A tree grows from the Earth (negative pole) to the sky (positive pole), thus wooden rafters and studs are fixed so as to have their positive pole towards the sky. To make sure a natural flow of energies between the construction and the biosphere is maintained the beams would have their positive pole towards North or East,

It is well known that our planet, being a great magnet has positive and negative poles, It is surrounded by its own magnetic field (the geomagnetic field) which is pulsating at the rate of 7, 8 beats/second. Location and hour of the day determines its field intensity. Underground water streams and geological faults cause magnetic disturbances. Multistoried and massive construction without understanding the Earth energies can reduce the effects of the geomagnetic to the extent of inducing different health problems such as heart diseases. Scientists and Doctors in Germany and France have found that out of 400 deaths due to cancer revealed that 383 cases were related to dwelling over geological faults, underground water veins, and disturbances of the natural geomagnetic field. French beekeepers specifically place hives over underground water veins. Such hives can produce up to three times more honey than hives positioned a few feet away, but due to the impact of the negative vibrations the lifespan of these bees is shortened and they become aggressive.

Figure 4 effect of geostress on bed

Figure 5 origin of geostress below homes

Figure 6 geo-energy grids and lightning

1.5. What is Geo Stress

The subtle vibrations coming from mother Earth has an impact on our health and can cause chronic diseases is a difficult proposition to be explained to modern educated, pragmatic person.

Since millions of years, we have lived with this natural vibration which rises up through Earth's mantle. Subterranean running water, certain mineral concentrations, fault lines and underground cavities when encounters with these natural vibrations, their original vibrations become distorted and harmful to living organisms. In the case of running water, normally 100 to 300 ft. (30 to 90 meters) underground, an electromagnetic field is created in the opposite direction to its flow by friction which then increases these vibrations passing through by up to 30 times.

Geopathic stress is the phenomenon which is the effect of these higher vibrations, also known as negative energies or harmful Earth rays. Human, plants, and animals if resides on this Earth would feel discomfort and ill health.

Normally, each day and each minute we are in tune with these natural Earth vibrations but it does not affect us during a short duration. These essential natural vibrations have a negative effect on human energies only when spending extended time in a still position, sleeping rooms and working offices are spaces which need to be checked for geostresses

Immunity and general wellbeing are compromised with the effect of geostress. Continuous spending time on geostress areas may result in diseases in the periodic time frame. Disturbances in sleep patterns, restlessness and/or chronic lethargy and poor health would be initial symptoms of geostress. If not treated and if the position of bed or office desk is not shifted this stress can eventually generate more complex diseases or prolong your recovery from illness. Proper Absorption of vitamins, minerals, trace elements etc from your food (and supplements) can be delayed or prevented when you are staying on geostress zone. Also, geostress can often make you allergic to food, drinks, and environmental pollution.

1.6. The layers of Geobiology

The purpose of Geobiology is to provide information to enable us to reproduce a space as near to natural living conditions as possible, taking into consideration the need for the comfort provided by ancient and modern technologies favorable to the environment.

The quality of our home and the elements necessary as basic ingredient is defined by geobiology. Several elements, factors and layers determine a peaceful house with the right balance. These elements are in three interdependent levels.

- *The Physical Level* deals with all the known effects related to the quality of the Earth (i.e. geological fault, water streams, Radon...etc.), to the quality of the location (i.e. air pollution, noise...etc.) and the quality of the building construction. Building materials have a great influence on our health, both physical and psychological. We can easily imagine ourselves stroking a piece of wood, feeling its softness and warmth. The tree has grown out from the energies of the soil, the water, and the cosmos, it radiates a message of life, very different from the message of a piece of vinyl or plastic. Even the best of natural materials can become hazardous by toxic chemical treatments which are slowly releasing unhealthy emanations such as Lead, Cadmium, Formaldehyde, Phenols, Organochlorine...etc. They can cause human discomforts such as nausea, headaches, insomnia, asthma, brain damage and even chronic diseases like cancer
- *The Energy Level* includes the placement of a house on the energy grid, Curry or Hartmann nodal points and other tellurian currents, electromagnetic pollution and the Faraday cage effect due to poor earthing of electric devices, reinforcement of concrete slabs and steel frames. Lately, the use of artificial sources of radio electric frequencies has become a cause for concern. It has surpassed many times the production of natural sources., Electromagnetic pollution has increased a hundred times during the past 30 years as per German specialist Wolfgang Volkrodt. Low-frequency electromagnetic fields around high voltage power lines are a major cause of cancers affecting 10 to 15 % American children, this is the astonishing fact given by the New York Power Lines Project. This research group was formed by the commission responsible for the power grid of the State of New York.
- *The Symbolic or Spiritual Level*, which is the least recognized, is also the most important as it is the quality of the whole. Most of us can feel clearly the difference of feelings in extremes (i.e. between burial or cremation spaces and churches) and are getting affected, people who are more sensitive will perceive subtle differences that would nevertheless unconsciously influence us. According to B. Merz (Institute of Geobiology of Chardonne, Lausanne in Switzerland) just as space, where we spend time, can make us prone to disease or depression, another environment or vastu (in the Indian context)can lift us to more subtle levels of vibration, strengthening our body and spirit. Throughout history, such places are often sought after and are called sacred spaces. Tourist or modern pilgrims are often inspired by such power spots which our forefather already knew, Indian, Aborigines, Aryans and others have made several monuments and temples on these spots. Obeying a sacred tradition many man-made poles of attraction were built on powerful sites by the architect - priests, like the pyramids of Egypt, the statues of Easter Island or many Gothic cathedrals. The Celts considered the site on which the cathedral of Chartres is erected as sacred.

All past energetic imprints are recorded by land. Water and Earth has long-lasting memory. A divergence from its ideal natural condition would create disharmony. It becomes necessary to clear stagnant vibrations and energies from your home, office or property to make it return it to its original state of perfection. change the quality of your environment, creating a sacred space for living and working. To change the quality of your environment and creating a sacred space for living and working, energy sciences such as spiritual Vastu, Energetic Feng Shui, and Geophysics Clearing is utilized. By connecting and working co-creatively with Nature and applying quantum technologies, we can clear our habitats and Earth. Utilising the wisdom of our forefathers we can lift the vibrations of our communities, thereby healing ourselves and the planet. Geostress corrections can be done by connecting ourselves with the Spirit (energy) of the property then clearing the negative energy that runs through the grids of the Earth using a process and defined protocols. These cross grid lines when burdened with negative and noxious energy, affect the health and well-being of everything that lives on the property.

1.7. Case Studies

1.8. Sacred Biology – Kedarnath Temple, India

It is not surprising that this pilgrimage has been the subject of many miracles that can be attributed to many phenomena geobiological and spiritual presences.

Among the 12 Jyotirlingas (spiritual Indian sacred spaces) Kedarnath is the highest. This 1000-year-old and enormous temple is located in the Rudra Himalaya range in North of India. The mystery of this building's structure has mystified scientists for decades. The structure survived being buried under the snow for almost 400 years, with several yellow lines implying glacial movement over the stones. Glaciers in this region with mud and rocks can be really abrasive.

The building is 85 feet high, 187 feet long and 80 feet broad with walls of 12 feet breadth. The Kedarnath temple is built strategically on 6 feet high plinth following perfect Divine Proportions. Prithwe research team is working on this mystery, How this European system which was first discussed by Vitruvius in the first century before Christ reached India around 18 Century? How were 12-foot wide stones cut precisely and put together with such precision in a completely inaccessible part of North India with sub-zero temperatures?

Figures 7, 8, 9 Kedarnath Temple, Golden Ratio & Vastu Diagram

1.9. Urban Crime – Negative Energies in Pune City

Even as 11 accidents were reported on the Pune-Mumbai Expressway in the past four days, Ar Mayank Barjatya shows how he thinks the negative energy and other parts of the city could be measured, contained and how it affects crime. He has been studying the crime hotspots of the city. Eight years ago, he had suggested that the police could reduce the negative energy by placing harmonizers in these spots.

Barjatya's studies showed that the crime rate has been very strong in the south of Pune, in areas like Sahakar Nagar, Gultekdi, and Wanowrie and in the north-west of the city — Pimple Gurav, Spicer College etc. A zonal map showing the spots with the highest criminal activities was prepared accordingly.

Barjatya demonstrated some of his research for Pune Mirror by actually taking readings on apparatuses named the Lekar antenna, the Esmog Spion and the Geo Magnetometer in Lulla Nagar-Kondhwa and Sangamwadi Bridge, two areas marked as crime hotspots. The apparatus showed the negative energy readings confirming Barjatya's theory. In Lulla Nagar and Kondhwa, the reading showed cosmic energy vibrating at a frequency of 12 acu units: negative 2.8 (bad for mental strength and creates confusion); global vibrations at a frequency of 15.3 acu units: negative 2.2 (poor for relationships and generate antisocial thinking); telluric vibrations of frequency 8 acu units: negative 2.3 (signalling financial weakness and unemployment).

The Esmog Spion showed geo stress at electromagnetic readings of a high frequency: 12,000 units at all levels which is high radiation and affects brain cells and generates anti-social thinking. At Wakdewadi, near the new bridge, the readings were almost the same. The police have now started compiling fresh data as statistics have

obviously changed over the past eight years. Police Inspector (Crime Branch) Sunil Tambe told Pune Mirror, “Barjatya has spoken to me. We are compiling the statistics and it will be completed soon.”.

Figures 10: Geostress measurement near Crime area & map of Pune city showing crime zones

1.10. Road Fatalities – A Geopathic Perspective

Ancient Science of Architecture can help avert accidents on Mumbai-Pune Expressway.

The 96-km Pune-Mumbai expressway has become synonymous with the fatal accidents, that seem to be happening at regular intervals other than a scenic drive. It is very common to open the day's papers and find news about an accident that has taken place on the expressway.

A Pune based research academy has conducted a fresh survey of accident-prone spots on highways at this alarming rate of accidents on the Expressway has taken so many innocent lives.

The survey was undertaken on the cause of these accidents by Ar. Mayank Barjatya and his team at the Vastuworld Academy, has given some interesting findings,

According to Ar. Barjatya, the high-accident spots (black spots) on the Mumbai-Pune Expressway is directly situated on geopathic stress zones, which exert a strong debilitating impact on the physiological condition of the vehicle drivers. These zones could cause critical errors while driving.

After a careful study using scientific devices like Geomagnetometer, Lecher Antenna, and Esmog spion Mayank Barjatya and research team of Vastuworld has identified seven spots on the expressway, where a number of accidents have taken place in the past few years. Each of these spots has been visited by a research team has checked for telluric and other geopathic stresses.

Thus, kind of detection work has been done in western countries with a great deal of success, Ar. Mayank reveals, not exactly on express highways but the same protocols have been used to find a strong correlation between crime and geopathic stress.

In the first year the crime in Denver where these geopathic harmonizers where installed went down 36% and the second year it went down 51%.' He adds further, “Now we have reported in from Los Angeles and San Diego, as well as San Francisco areas where they are working with the harmonizers and clearing the geopathic stress in their areas. They all report a reduction in crime. In San Diego (the first year of the project which started there in March of 1997), there is a 28% decline in drive-by shootings from the previous year. Homicide rates are down 15.2% from last year, and robberies are down 31%.”

It goes without saying that Geopathy and accidents are related. How can use the modern system of quantum science and utilize the development in instrumentation to absorb these vibrations ?.

Modern scientific society needs to accept these life-saving systems and should give a thought to these solutions.

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